

DTU Tradeit

A. M. Eberhard¹, O. Ellinghausen¹, M. Gjøen¹, Kristensen¹, A. Badman² and L. O. N. Arstad³

¹DTU Mechanical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

²DTU Civil Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

³DTU Management Engineering, Technical University of Denmark

INTRODUCTION

All around new products are being bought while the old model still works. These used models should not go to waste. DTU Tradeit will give students at DTU a chance to save and earn some money and thereby prolonging the life cycle of the products.

DTU TRADEIT

DTU Tradeit consists of a Facebook group that is already launched. Here students can trade all kinds of necessities between themselves. It is intended to evolve into a shop, which is described later in the text. Every year students are coming and going at DTU. Both Danish and foreign students. They all need new products and necessities to get settled and make a home while studying at DTU. As a students you do not have a lot of money but you still need some necessities and other things that you just want to have.

SURVEY

63 exchange and international students answered a survey that was send out as a part of the project. It was discovered that they bought many different necessities at a variety of trading platforms when arriving as a student at DTU. Some took more than 4 weeks to get settled in. The students also need to get rid of these necessities before they leave and hopefully get some of their money back. Some tries to sell their necessities, some are giving it away while others are throwing it out. A great opportunity is to bring the necessities from the students at one semester to the students at the next semester. Here the DTU Tradeit Shop comes into the picture.

DTU TRADEIT SHOP

The goal is that a DTU Tradeit Shop will be established on DTU Campus. Thereby the foreign students can go there and get their necessities quickly upon arrival and are able to get some of their money back when leaving by selling it back to the shop and making it available for the students the following semester. The shop will contain the most traded items while the rest can be traded in the Facebook group online. The plan it to get some resources through sponsorships and thereby having a constant stock at the high point of trading season.